

CAPILLARY-ENHANCED NON-AUTOCLAVE COMPOSITE MANUFACTURING BASED ON NANOPOROUS NETWORKS

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Keywords: manufacturing, void, capillary, carbon nanotube, nanoporous network

ABSTRACT

A composite manufacturing technique based on the capillary action of a nanoporous network is investigated to address the limitations of current manufacturing methods such as autoclave and out-of-autoclave prepreg processes. This manufacturing technique consists of the insertion of a nanoporous network (i.e., vertically aligned carbon nanotube arrays) into the interlaminar regions of composite laminates. Void content and mechanical tests suggest that this capillary-driven manufacturing technique enables traditional autoclave-required prepreg to be processed under vacuum-only conditions without an autoclave or any modifications to the prepreg system. Since conventional autoclave prepreps have been widely used in the aerospace industries and their material properties have been extensively researched, this manufacturing technique can enable high-quality composite structures to be achieved in a much more efficient way.

1 INTRODUCTION

The manufacturing of aerospace structural composites such as carbon fiber reinforced polymers has conventionally been performed through an autoclave to achieve high fiber volume fraction and low porosity. During the autoclave process, a laminate comprised of prepreg sheets is cured under a vacuum bagged condition with applied pressure of ~0.6 MPa to suppress the formation of voids. However, composite manufacturing with an autoclave is accompanied by high acquisition and operating costs due to the nature of convective heat transfer and the use of a pressurized vessel. Recently, the out-of-autoclave (OoA) prepreg, which is specially formulated to be cured in an oven, has been developed to overcome such disadvantages of an autoclave [1]. However, there are still several drawbacks, such as additional debulk steps due to a different type of matrix in OoA prepreps. OoA prepreg is accompanied by alteration of the resin composition to prevent the off-gas emission during curing [2] and modification of prepreg morphology for the void extraction channels [1]. Moreover, from a manufacturing point of view, even the use of OoA prepreps is not a completely ideal alternative. The heat transfer mechanism is still based on convection, leading to thermal inefficiencies, spatial temperature gradients in a laminate, and stress due to convective-to-conductive interactions between the heating gas medium and the cure materials [3]. As a consequence, part-to-part variability may occur after processing. Additionally, the fabrication process is still limited because it requires a fixed geometry. Given such limitations, further improvements are needed to realize an “actual” non-autoclave process that addresses the fundamental limitations of autoclave processing.

The approach here demonstrates a vacuum-bag-only manufacturing process for traditional autoclave prepreps, for which material properties have been extensively researched and qualified in industry. In the case of traditional autoclave prepreps, vacuum-bag-only processing without applied pressure often exhibits a high level of void content in the interlaminar regions [4]. Therefore, achieving a low void content in the interlaminar region is the primary challenge in non-autoclave processes. In this study, we present a non-autoclave prepreg process by replacing the applied pressure of an autoclave with the capillary pressure of a nanoporous network (NPN). This study demonstrates

that one can manufacture aerospace-grade composites from autoclave-required prepregs without modifying their matrix system and morphology.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The demonstration of the capillary-driven non-autoclave manufacturing process was conducted in two-fold: (1) investigation of the effect of NPN placement within a laminate; (2) fabrication of composite laminates by using the non-autoclave manufacturing process and subsequent evaluation of the laminate physical properties as compared to autoclave-cured composite laminates.

2.1 Synthesis of Nanoporous Network (NPN)

Vertically aligned carbon nanotube arrays with heights of 20-30 μm were used as the NPN in this study. To synthesize carbon nanotube (CNT) arrays, a thermal catalytic chemical vapor deposition process was used with a quartz tube furnace of 2-inch diameter at atmospheric pressure, which is similar to a previously reported process [5–8]. Ethylene was used as the carbon source, and 600 ppm of water was added to the helium gas. The as-grown CNT arrays consisted of multiwalled CNTs having 3-7 walls [9] with an average inner and outer diameter of ≈ 5.1 nm and ≈ 7.8 nm, respectively. The volume fraction of CNT arrays corresponded to $\approx 1.6\%$ with intrinsic CNT density of ≈ 1.6 g/cm^3 and average inter-CNT spacing of ≈ 59 nm.

2.2 Study of NPN Placement

In this study, three configurations were tested to evaluate the effect of NPN placement as follows: a laminate without NPN (“Control”); a laminate with NPNs at 7 interlaminar regions in the middle (“Mid”); a laminate with NPNs at all 15 interlaminar regions (“All”). Hexcel AS4/8552 and IM7/8552 aerospace-grade unidirectional (UD) carbon fiber prepregs were used. It should be noted that these prepregs are designed to be processed with applied pressure using an autoclave. For the laminates, 16 plies of 3 cm \times 3 cm were used in the quasi-isotropic layup of $[0/90/+45/-45]_{2S}$, and the NPNs were installed in the interlaminar regions during hand-layup process. The nominal laminate thickness of AS4/8552 and IM7/8552 correspond to 2.08 mm and 2.10 mm, respectively. The laminates were cured at the same time using a hot plate (i.e., EchoTherm HS60A) so that batch-to-batch thermal variations were minimized. For the curing process, the recommended vacuum bagging procedure from the prepreg manufacturer was followed [10]. The cure materials used were standard for composite prepreg processing and included a vacuum bagging film (Airtech WL8400), guaranteed nonporous Teflon (GNPT) film (Airtech Release Ease 234 TFNP), sealant tape (Airtech GS-213-3), and air breather (Airtech Ultraweave 606). After the hand lay-up process of the laminates, vacuum debulking was performed on the full laminates at room temperature for 3 hours. During the cure cycle, the recommended cure cycle in the technical data sheet was followed, and the vacuum bag was kept under full vacuum (i.e., >29.5 inHg) during the entire process. Both prepreg systems are designed to have the same temperature for the thermal process as follows: cure temperature of 110 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a hold time of 60 min, and then cure temperature of 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a hold time of 120 min and a ramp rate of 3 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

2.3 Composite Laminate Fabrication

By utilizing the results of NPN placement, the composite laminates comprised of Hexcel AS4/8552 were fabricated to examine whether the laminates processed with NPN but without an autoclave have comparable physical properties to conventionally manufactured laminates (i.e., cured by an “Autoclave”). Here, the laminates with NPN were cured by an out-of-oven (OoO) curing method to entirely remove the need for a heating vessel and to demonstrate an actual non-autoclave composite manufacturing process (hereafter “OoO with NPN”). In addition to Autoclave and OoO with NPN, the composite laminates were also processed by a hotplate only under vacuum and without an autoclave’s pressure to compare the effect of insufficient pressure (hereafter “Hotplate”). Sixteen plies (nominal laminate thickness of 2.08 mm) of 60 mm \times 60 mm were used in a unidirectional layup of $[0]_{16}$ and

quasi-isotropic layup of $[0/90/+45/-45]_{2S}$. In the case of unidirectional layup, small angles ($\pm 2^\circ$) between the plies were introduced intentionally to avoid fiber nesting [11].

For the conventional autoclave curing process (i.e., Autoclave), the recommended cure procedure from the prepreg manufacturer was followed using an autoclave [10]. The conditions were provided as follows: cure temperature of 110°C with a hold time of 60 min, and post-cure temperature of 180°C with a hold time of 120 min; ramp rate at $3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$; autoclave gauge pressure of 0.6 MPa with a vacuum. For the vacuum-only (i.e., Hotplate) curing process, the same vacuum bagging procedure for the autoclave process above was used. Once a vacuum bag was prepared for the cure, the laminate and cure materials were placed on a hot plate (EchoTherm HS60A) for curing. During the cure cycle, the same curing condition in the technical data sheet was followed without applied pressure of 0.6 MPa. For the OoO curing (i.e., OoO with NPN), based on the results of NPN placement, the NPNs were introduced to all 15 interlaminar regions within 16-ply laminates for the OoO-cured specimens. The cure setup in the previous study was used (see Figure 1 for the vacuum bagging setup of the OoO curing) [7,12]. Also, thermal insulating blocks made of calcium silicate were installed to reduce the heat lost to the environment. The CNT heaters were placed on the top and bottom surfaces of the prepared 16-ply laminates so that the active heating area of $60\text{ mm} \times 60\text{ mm}$ exactly matched to the dimension of the laminates. A DC power supply was connected to the electrodes of each heater to control the input power to follow the specific cure cycle. The vacuum bagging setup was placed on a lab bench, and the temperature was measured by thermocouples (OMEGA Engineering fast-response K-type) that were attached to the heaters. The input voltage, current, and power consumption were monitored during a cure cycle and controlled by an on-off control system.

2.4 Void Content Analysis

μCT imaging of laminates was performed with ZEISS Xradia 520 Versa at the Institute for Soldier Nanotechnologies, MIT. An isotropic voxel size of $\sim 1.5\ \mu\text{m}$ was used with an X-ray beam energy of 7 W at 80 kV. For each scan, 3201 2D-projections were acquired while a specimen was rotated 360° . The exposure time for each projection was 1 second, and the projection radiographs were reconstructed using the embedded software in the μCT machine. The reconstructed 3D volumes were analyzed with ImageJ following ASTM E1441. The void content can be easily calculated by applying a threshold filter to differentiate voids from other components of composites such as polymer matrix and fibers.

2.5 Degree of Cure (DoC) Analysis

After the curing was completed using the autoclave and OoO processes, differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) was conducted using a Discovery DSC (TA instruments) to evaluate the degree of cure (DoC) of the laminate. The dynamic DSC run was performed by scanning the heat flow from

Figure 1. Vacuum bag lay-up of the OoO curing process with two-sided CNT heaters.

40 °C to 300 °C at a 5 °C/min ramp rate. The DoC was estimated by comparing the area of the exothermic peak observed in the DSC curve of the heat-processed laminate, also known as the heat of reaction, to that of an uncured laminate. The DSC specimens were taken from the top, middle, and bottom parts of a laminate so that the through-thickness variation of the DoC was assessed.

2.6 Mechanical Testing

The short beam shear (SBS) test was conducted based on ASTM standard D2344 to assess the short-beam strength. The dimension of a specimen was nominally 12 mm × 4 mm × 2 mm ($L \times W \times t$), and these specimens were taken from the 60 mm × 60 mm unidirectional laminates comprised of 16 plies of AS4/8552 UD prepreg. The cut laminate edges were polished with 800, 1200, and 2400 grit sandpapers to avoid rough or uneven surfaces, which may result in pre-cracks, following the standard. A three-point bend fixture with a loading nose of 6 mm, supports of 3 mm diameter steel cylinders, and a span length of 8 mm was used. During the tests, the force applied to the specimen was monitored at a rate of crosshead movement of 1.0 mm/min applied by a Zwick/Roell Z010 mechanical testing machine. The short-beam strength (σ_{SBS}) was then calculated using the equation as follows:

$$\sigma_{SBS} = 0.75 \times \frac{P_f}{w_{SBS} \times t_{SBS}} \quad (1)$$

where P_f , w_{SBS} , and t_{SBS} are the load at the failure observed during the test, the width, and the thickness of the specimen, respectively.

In addition, dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was conducted to evaluate the thermophysical properties of the fabricated laminates. The specimen dimensions and testing procedure were carried out based on the ASTM standard D7028. A dynamic mechanical analyzer (TA Q850 DMA) was used for the characterization of the composite laminates. All DMA tests were conducted using a three-point bending fixture with a span of 50 mm, which is ideal for composite materials due to its simpler stress distribution than that induced in a single or double cantilever configuration, and measurable strain for high modulus materials [13]. For the DMA tests, 16-ply unidirectional laminates cured by autoclave and OoO curing processes were used. Five specimens of 60 mm × 60 mm × 2 mm ($L \times W \times t$) for both the Autoclave and OoO with NPN laminates were tested in the temperature range of 40 °C to 300 °C at a 2 °C/min heating rate, maximum displacement of 50 μm, and multi-frequency sweep of 1, 3.2, 10, and 30 Hz. The storage modulus, loss modulus, and tan delta were obtained *via* the DMA test, and the glass transition temperature (T_g) was determined from the storage modulus and tan delta curves. The multi-frequency sweep results were analyzed to estimate the activation energy of the glass transition relaxation as an additional comparator of the autoclave vs. OoO manufacturing methods. The estimation of the activation energy was determined *via* T_g from the tan delta peak due to the accuracy and consistency of this method [13–16]. The monitoring of the activation energy is correlated to the modulus and compliance of a composite at the end of the service life, and therefore is additionally useful in assessing environmental exposure and aging of the material [14,16–18]. The estimation of the activation energy is based on the effect of temperature on the frequency of molecular conformational changes in polymers [18,19]. Such a phenomenon can be explained by the Arrhenius relationship: the increase in frequency leads to the shift of the tan delta curve toward higher temperature. The activation energy can be estimated by obtaining the slope of the $\ln f$ vs. $1/T_g$ with the equation as follows [13]:

$$\Delta H = -R \frac{d(\ln f)}{d\left(\frac{1}{T_g}\right)} \quad (2)$$

where ΔH is the activation energy (kJ/mol) for the glass transition relaxation, R is the universal gas constant (J/mol K), f is the testing frequency (Hz), and T_g is the glass transition temperature in Kelvin (K).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Void content, degree of cure (DoC), dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA), and short beam shear strength (SBS) are used to compare laminates manufactured via autoclave and OoO with NPN.

3.1 Effect of NPN Placement on Void Reduction

Figure 2 shows representative μ CT slices of AS4/8552 and IM7/8852 laminates in three NPN placement cases (i.e., “Control”, “Mid”, and “All”). The areas where NPNs were installed are indicated in Figure 2. In X-ray micrographs, the brighter gray-scaled regions denote denser areas such as fibers and polymers, while the voids appear as darker. The quantified void contents from 40 slices for each case are presented in Figure 3. Of note, in the case of the “Mid” specimen, void contents were quantified in two separate regions depending on the existence of NPN. The “Control” specimens cured without applied pressure showed a void fraction of $\approx 2.4\%$ and $\approx 1.0\%$ in AS4/8552 and IM7/8552, respectively. This is because vacuum alone is not sufficient to remove voids or to suppress the void formation within a laminate. However, when NPNs were installed in the interlaminar regions on the middle of the laminates (see the “Mid” case), the void contents of AS4/8552 and IM7/8552 were substantially reduced in the middle part where NPNs were introduced. Moreover, there was no detectable void in the middle part of the IM7/8552 laminate. On the contrary, the outer regions without NPNs showed a high void content ($> 1\%$) as much as the “Control” specimens did. In the case of “All”, the AS4/8552 and IM7/8552 laminates showed very low void content ($< 0.1\%$), which is comparable with the quality of autoclave-cured laminate. The results concluded that NPNs significantly reduced the voids in the regions where they were installed. Therefore, in order to manufacture a void-free laminate, NPNs need to be installed in all interlaminar regions.

Figure 2. μ CT slices of AS4/8552 and IM7/8852 depending on NPN placement.

Figure 3. Void content of AS4/8552 and IM7/8552 composite laminates cured under a vacuum without NPN (Control), with NPNs only in the middle half of the laminate (Mid), and with NPNs in all interlaminar regions (All).

3.2 Application of Capillary-driven Void Reduction in Advanced Composite Laminates

3.2.1 Void Content Results

Figure 4(a) shows representative μ CT slices of three manufacturing conditions (i.e., Autoclave, Hotplate, and OoO with NPN). The quantified void contents from 100 slices at 5 different scanning positions for each condition are presented in Figure 4(b). As seen in Figure 4(a), there are no detectable voids in the specimens cured by an autoclave (i.e., Autoclave) under a voxel size of ≈ 1.5 μm , as expected. In contrast, the specimens cured by the hot plate without applied pressure (i.e., Hotplate) resulted in a void fraction of $\approx 2.39\%$. Such high void contents of these specimens corroborate that applied pressure is required to lower the final void content when curing autoclave prepreg systems. Also, it should be noted that most of the voids are located in the interlaminar regions, which may result in degrading the interlaminar-related mechanical properties of the laminates [20–22]. However, when the OoO curing process and NPN were introduced in the interlaminar regions (i.e., OoO with NPN), the void content was significantly reduced. Interestingly, the OoO with NPN specimens did not contain any detectable voids through 3D tomography characterization, which is the same result as the Autoclave specimens. As reported in the studies on aligned CNT interlaminar reinforcement [23–25], no substantial morphological difference in the interlaminar regions before and after the insertion of the aligned CNTs as NPN were observed. Furthermore, there were no morphological differences such as ply thickness between the OoO with NPN and conventional specimens under high-resolution X-ray micrographs. Therefore, we demonstrate that NPN helps to reduce the voids in the interlaminar regions and that the integration with OoO curing enables void-free composite laminates to be manufactured.

3.2.2 Degree of Cure Results

DoC *via* DSC was used to compare the thermophysical attributes of the OoO with NPN specimens with those of the Autoclave specimens. Three DSC specimens were prepared from the top, center, and bottom part of a quasi-isotropic laminate for each case to establish through-thickness spatial trends in DoC. The mean value of the heat of reaction (~ 194 J/g) acquired from three uncured prepreg plies was used for the calculation of DoC. The expected range of DoC for oven manufacturing for this material is in the range of 90–95% (per the manufacturer), which is typical of most oven and autoclave processed aerospace-grade composites.

Figure 4. Void Contents of composite laminates cured under an autoclave with applied pressure (Autoclave), a hot plate without applied pressure (Hotplate), and OoO curing with NPN (OoO with NPN). (a) Representative μ CT slices of each manufacturing condition, and (b) quantified void content of the composite laminates.

As presented in Figure 5, the DoCs of both Autoclave and OoO with NPN specimens are in the target range. To determine whether the means of the Autoclave and OoO with NPN specimens are statistically different, Welch's t-test was conducted. A p-value less than 0.05 was used to establish a statistical difference with 95% confidence. The DoCs of the OoO with NPN laminate showed no statistical difference from those of the Autoclave laminate. The previous study without thermal insulation found that the DoC of a laminate strongly depends on the thermal distribution within the laminate [3]. Thus, the results imply that thermal distributions within the laminates were uniform. Overall, the OoO with NPN laminate showed the equivalent thermal properties of the Autoclave laminate.

3.2.3 Short-beam Strength

The results of SBS tests were evaluated to compare the mechanical properties of laminates cured under different manufacturing conditions. Ten specimens were tested for each manufacturing

condition. Even though the short-beam strength may not directly indicate the interlaminar shear strength of the laminate due to its complex stress distribution, and the failure can be a combination of different failure modes such as discrete and irregular interlaminar shear, tension, compression, and plastic deformation [26], it is generally accepted that the SBS testing can be used for comparison of batch and as a screening tool for composite laminate properties with a description of the failure mode [27,28]. Figure 6 shows the short-beam strength of each manufacturing condition. In all cases, the interlaminar shear failure was observed among several failure modes described in the standard ASTM D2344. The autoclave-cured specimens (i.e., Autoclave) exhibited a short-beam strength of ≈ 98.8 MPa. However, due to the high void content, the vacuum-only hotplate-cured (i.e., Hotplate) specimens showed a $\approx 23\%$ decrease in the short-beam strength, compared to the autoclave-cured specimens. The result lends support to the previous reports that matrix-dominated properties are degraded by the existence of voids [20–22,29,30]. Interestingly, the OoO with NPN specimens did not exhibit any decrease in the short-beam strength. The OoO with NPN specimens showed a short-beam strength of ≈ 98.0 MPa, which is comparable to that of Autoclave specimens. As presented, a p -value of 0.37 indicates that the mean values of short-beam strength are not statistically different from each other.

Figure 5. Comparison of degree of cure as evaluated spatially via DSC at the top, center, and bottom plies of 16-ply laminate for autoclave and OoO with NPN.

3.2.4 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

The results from the DMA curves, including the storage modulus, loss modulus, and tan delta, suggest that the Autoclave and OoO with NPN specimens have the same dynamic mechanical responses (see Figure 7(a) for the representative storage modulus, loss modulus, and tan delta curve from DMA tests on the specimens at the testing frequency of 1 Hz). Figure 7(b) shows the storage modulus and loss modulus at 100 °C. The results of the p -value in the two curves ($p=0.50$ for the storage modulus; $p=0.33$ for the loss modulus) indicated that there was no significant difference in the curves of the Autoclave and OoO with NPN specimens. The T_g values determined by the storage modulus curves and tan delta curves at 1 Hz frequency, and the estimated activation energy values from the multi-frequency sweeps at 1, 3.2, 5, and 30 Hz are summarized in Table 1. For the estimation of activation energy, the T_g values determined by the tan delta curves were used due to the high accuracy of this method [13–16]. The OoO with NPN specimens exhibited ~ 5 °C higher T_g in both curves than the autoclave specimens. It should be noted that the T_g values of 205 °C and 230 °C from the storage modulus and tan delta curves were

Figure 6. Results of the short beam shear tests of AS4/8552 quasi-isotropic laminates under different types of curing (autoclave curing without NPN, vacuum-only hot plate curing without NPN, and OoO curing with NPN).

reported with a 5 °C/min ramp-up rate, respectively. It is known that the T_g measured by DMA curves may vary by up to 25 °C depending on the parameters and methodology for testing [16,31]. The Autoclave and the OoO with NPN specimens exhibited statistically no difference in activation energy as shown in Table 1. The DMA tests indicated that the Autoclave and OoO with NPN specimens showed comparable dynamic properties of the polymer within the laminates.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a nanoporous network (NPN) comprised of vertically aligned carbon nanotube arrays was utilized to address the limitations of the current composite laminate manufacturing methods, such as autoclave processing. We demonstrated that the insertion of a NPN into the interlaminar regions of composite laminates replaced the need for applied pressure from an autoclave by instead utilizing capillary pressure from the nanoporous array characteristics. From the void content analysis *via* micro-computed X-ray tomography, it was found that the interlaminar regions with NPN showed no detectable voids, and therefore void-free composites were able to be manufactured without an autoclave. The thermal and mechanical tests (i.e., degree of cure, short beam shear test, and dynamic mechanical analysis) showed that the manufactured composite laminates *via* out-of-oven conductive curing and NPN-based processes had equivalent properties with the autoclave-cured composite laminates. This capillary-driven composite manufacturing technique enables traditional autoclave-required prepregs to be processed only under vacuum without any modifications in resin chemistry, and therefore an actual non-autoclave was demonstrated. Since autoclave prepregs have been widely used in industry and their material properties have been extensively researched, this new manufacturing process enables high-quality composite architectures to be achieved in a much more efficient way, overcoming the limitations of conventional composite manufacturing processes.

Figure 7. DMA results. (a) Representative storage modulus, loss modulus, and tan delta curve from DMA tests at the testing frequency of 1 Hz for autoclave and OoO with NPN specimens, and (b) storage modulus and loss modulus at 100 °C of the autoclave and OoO with NPN specimens.

Specimen number	T _g from storage modulus (°C)		T _g from tan delta (°C)		Activation Energy (kJ/mol)	
	Autoclave	OoO w/ NPN	Autoclave	OoO w/ NPN	Autoclave	OoO w/ NPN
1	226.11	231.70	240.84	245.82	772.94	797.75
2	227.50	233.75	239.71	244.41	781.82	752.82
3	226.98	232.21	240.97	243.42	784.70	751.32
4	228.47	231.50	238.86	245.03	777.13	756.88
5	227.79	231.79	239.63	245.09	742.47	755.20
Average	227.37	232.19	240.00	244.75	771.81	762.79
Standard Error	0.40	0.41	0.40	0.40	7.61	8.79
p-value	3.04E-05		2.86E-05		0.46	

Table 1. Glass transition temperature (T_g) and activation energy of relaxation of the Autoclave and OoO with NPN laminates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work presented herein was funded by the Department of the Navy under STTR Phase I Contract N18B-T031. This work was partially supported by Airbus, ANSYS, Embraer, Lockheed Martin, Saab AB, Saertex, and Teijin Carbon America through MIT's Nano-Engineered Composite aerospace Structures (NECST) Consortium. This work made use of the facilities at the Institute for Soldier Nanotechnologies at MIT, supported (in part) by the U.S. Army Research Laboratory and the U.S. Army Research Office through the Institute for Soldier Nanotechnologies, under contract number W911NF-13-D-0001. Micro-computed tomography instrumentation support by the Office of Naval Research (ONR) under grant number ONR.N000141712068 through the Defense University Research Instrumentation Program (DURIP) is gratefully acknowledged. The authors kindly thank Saab AB for donation of the AS4/8552 autoclave prepreg.

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